

Deliverable 7.7

CHORIZO'S IMPACT ASSESSMENT

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Glossary of terms and acronyms

Acronym/Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Loss & Waste
CA	Consortium Agreement
CS	Case study
FW	Food Waste
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FWCI	Field-Weighted Citation Index
FWVI	Field-Weighted View Impact
GA	Grant Agreement
MOA	Motivation Opportunity Abilities
S-TR	Short-term result

Executive summary

The deliverable D7.7 “CHORIZO Impact assessment” provides an overview of the impacts achieved by the CHORIZO project, as defined by the objectives and commitments in the Grant Agreement. Horizon Europe supports research that can have a significant impact on science, society and economy. The Grant Agreement (Part B, Section 2.1) defines the indicators and impacts to be achieved and accordingly, CHORIZO, through task 7.4 established a structured monitoring framework, updated every six months, to track progress through a series of short-term results. D7.7 consolidates the results and provides the overall impact assessment which is based on both internal monitoring and input from external stakeholders.

From a scientific point of view, CHORIZO is expected to create high-quality new knowledge on the impact of FLW prevention/reduction actions and the influence of social norms on FLW behaviour. Only a few other projects have integrated behavioural and social norm insights into empirical research in such a depth. This was put into practice through the creation of evaluation frameworks, the FLW actions database and the CHORIZO Index. Concurrently, the case studies across households, hospitality, schools, food banks and retail, provided real-world evidence about the scientific findings and ensured their practical application and transferability.

From a societal point of view, CHORIZO is expected to contribute to changing social norms towards zero food waste. CHORIZO has engaged actors across the food supply chain with the development of training and education packages and capacity-building initiatives. The case studies demonstrate how the insights can be translated into practice and embedded into prevention practices in everyday contexts, for instance by improving awareness in school settings. This has also been reinforced by communication and dissemination activities, connecting the outputs and findings with other EU Initiatives and projects.

From an economic and technological point of view, CHORIZO is expected to deliver tangible tools and services to generate innovation-based growth. These resources, notably the CHORIZO Insider Databank and the OFLW Visualizer/Rapid Appraisal Tool, allow food actors to access evidence-based guidance, evaluate the performance of their initiatives and assess the outcomes of different methodologies. Again, the integration of behavioural insights in digital tools represents an innovative contribution to the FLW management, with a stronger emphasis on upstream prevention.

The deliverable documents how CHORIZO addresses critical gaps in the FLW landscape. The project’s results are scientifically innovative, socially relevant and economically beneficial, contributing directly to EU policy priorities, Key Strategic Orientations and global goals. This novel approach blends behavioural insight with practical tools, case studies and training, backed by real-world evidence, showing strong potential for long term use across different parts of the food chain.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Impacts of CHORIZO

CHORIZO delivers several Scientific, Societal and Economic/Technological Impacts as defined in Section 2.1 of Part B of the GA and they are also presented in Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden. **(ANNEX I)** of this document. These impacts affect the scientific community, food businesses, policy makers, consumers, NGOs, food actors, schools, households, children, canteens, hotels, restaurants, food banks, food smart packaging and date marking companies, consumer associations, FW related associations, local governments, FLW-related IT, service developers etc.

Based on the time frame in which these impacts were expected to be achieved, they were categorized into short-term, medium-term and long-term impacts, where **short-term were delivered by the end of the project**, *medium-term* should be delivered *2 years after the end of the project* and *long-term impacts* are those that are expected to be achieved *about 10 years after the project completion*.

1.2 Short-term results (to be delivered by the end of the project)

As stipulated in the Grant Agreement, CHORIZO has to achieve 21 short-term results (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**), by the end of the project, consisting of 14 scientific, 5 social and 2 economic/technological results. These results can be further categorized considering the type of the results. In this regard, CHORIZO's short-term results are scientific articles, assessments of the engaged food actors on the project's products, products published open access and evidence that CHORIZO achieves reduction of FLW.

- Scientific results:
 - Four peer-reviewed publications advancing the evidence base on FLW
 - Eight documented cases of actors' engagement of project outputs
 - Two products published as open access
- Societal results:
 - Three food actors' engagement and contributions
 - Two cases providing evidence of FLW reduction
- Economic and technological results:
 - Two engagements with companies and practitioners indicating potential uptake

Overall, the conducted analysis provided that during the CHORIZO lifetime 4 short-term results with scientific articles will be accomplished (13 articles in total), 13 results require external actors' engagement and/or assessment, 2 project outcomes will be published open access (1 database of previous actions to reduce FLW and 3 project articles) and 2 results will provide evidence that CHORIZO may achieve FLW reduction.

2 IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

The impact assessment methodology implemented in CHORIZO can be depicted in the following Figure 1. Each result is related to a corresponding Work Package and a Deliverable. Most of the times, the result can be achieved only after the Due Date of this corresponding deliverable. Towards that, the Project’s Steering Committee has decided to assign a responsible partner for each result to act as a contact person and provide information on the status of each result.

Figure 1 Impact Assessment Methodology

Every six months the partners who were responsible for the results’ achievement provided information on the progress of their assigned result. INLECOM as the monitoring actor checked the validity of this information. If the result was not accomplished, the respective responsible partner provided a status description along with potential obstacles and mitigation strategies to be implemented. Furthermore, in order to enhance the monitoring process, they estimated the required time for achieving the result.

When the result in question was achieved, then a description of the actions taken towards achievement was provided, along with a relevant evaluation of the quality of the results. In some cases, for example, exceeding the short-term results would mean that also the medium-term results of the project are reasonable (please check ANNEX I for medium term results) and can be achieved 2 years after the Project completion. The assessment relies on pre-established criteria that have been agreed by the Project Steering Committee. These criteria are further elaborated in the subsequent sections.

2.1 Linking short-term results with WPs, Deliverables and responsible partners

The tables below display the linkage between **each short-term result**, and the corresponding: i) **ID**; ii) **WP**; iii) **Deliverable**; iv) the **Deliverable’s due date** (after which the result can be accomplished) and v) the assigned **responsible partner**.

For example, result with **ID 1** (2 peer-reviewed articles, describing the evidence-based analysis results), which was to be attained by the end of the project, is linked to **WP1** (Evidence based analysis and sector-specific guidance) and **Deliverable 1.2** (Evidence-based analysis of FLW actions/tools). Deliverable 1.2 was scheduled **for month 10**, indicating that the related short-term result can be accomplished after month 10, but **prior to the conclusion of the project**. As agreed, **VLTN** was the lead partner for the attainment of short-term result 1, as they delivered the evidence-based analysis (Lead Partner of D1.2).

Table 1 Linkage between each short-term result, and i) WP, ii) Deliverable, iii) Due date, iv) the responsible partners (scientific impact)

	ID	Short-term results <i>have to be achieved by the end of the Project</i>	Related WP	Related Del.	Due date <i>after which the short term result can be achieved.</i>	Who achieves the result?	
Scientific Impact	Impact pathway 1	1	2 peer-reviewed articles, describing the evidence-based analysis results	1	D1.2	M10	VLTN (ICLEI, UCPH, EV-ILVO)
		2	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the structure of the FLW index and its use in prioritising actions.	1	D1.3	M12	VLTN
		3	The sector-specific guidance is taken up by 1 food association to guide its members to better decision-making	1, 5, 6	D1.4	M15	EV-ILVO (FIAB)
		4	Acceptance of the CHORIZO Index by the EU FLW Prevention Hub team as reference for prioritising actions	1,6	D1.3	M12	VLTN
		5	The FLW actions' database, is accessed by >200 food actors	1	D1.2	M10	VLTN (EV-ILVO)
		6	Food actors that used the actions' database, assessed its contribution to their decision making with an avg. rating of 5 (7-step Likert scale)	1	D1.2	M10	VLTN (EV-ILVO)
	Impact pathway 2	7	6 peer-reviewed articles, presenting the interaction between social norms and FLW behaviour, based on the empirical data generated by the project (1 article per CS)	2	D2.3	M18	VLTN (NORCE, UNIBO, EV-ILVO, ITC, UCPH)
		8	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the Integrated MOA - HUMAT modelling framework, and its deployment in the project	3	D3.1	M11	UNIBO (NORCE)
		9	The FLW rapid appraisal tool, is accessed by >50 food actors	3,6	D3.5	M34	FIAB (UNIBO, CSCP)
		10	Food actors' assessment of the contribution of knowledge on social norms to their decision making (avg. rating: 5, in 7-step Likert scale)	3,6	D3.5	M34	FIAB (UNIBO, CSCP)
	Impact pathway 3	11	3 project articles to be provided as Open Access	1, 2, 3, 4	various	M1-36	various
		12	1 database of >300 previous FLW initiatives (classified into an FLW action taxonomy) to be provided as Open Access	1	D1.2	M10	VLTN (EV-ILVO)
		13	1 communication package (3 products) focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors	4,6	D4.2	M36	FIAB (UCPH, CSCP)
		14	1 science education package focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors	4,6	D4.3	M36	UCPH (ICLEI, FIAB, CSCP)

The monitoring process for the societal and the technological/economic impact has been identical. The related work packages, deliverables, and responsible partners for each short-term result are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Linkage between each short-term result, and i) WP, ii) Deliverable, iii) Due date, iv) the responsible partners (societal and technological/economic impact)

	ID	Short-term results <i>have to be achieved by the end of the Project</i>	Related WP	Related Del.	Due date <i>after which the short term result can be achieved.</i>	Who achieves the result?	
Societal impact	Impact pathway 4	15	Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 20% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused communication products, testified by the CS members (before vs after)	4	D4.2	M36	UCPH (EV-ILVO, CSCP, UNIBO, ICLEI, HFBA, CNTA, ITC, PCCI, FIAB, STRAWBERRY)
		16	Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 25% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused science education package, testified by 2 schools (before vs after)	4	D4.3	M36	UCPH (EV-ILVO, CSCP, ICLEI)
		17	Food actors' assessment of the influence that the project, communication, education & capacity building outputs, had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives (avg. rating: 4, in 7-step Likert scale)	4,6	D4.4	M35	FIAB (CSCP, UCPH)
	Impact pathway 5	18	Adoption of the CHORIZO communication products by 2 consumer associations, 2 European FW-related Associations, and 3 Local Governments	4,6	D4.2	M36	FIAB (UCPH)
		19	Adoption of the CHORIZO science education package by 2 schools	4,6	D4.3	M36	FIAB (UCPH)
Economic/technological impact	Impact pathway 6	20	5 providers and consumers of empirical evidence, share data based on specific rules through the CHORIZO 'Insighter' datahub	2,6	D2.2	M12	FIAB (EV-ILVO)
		21	2 companies express their formal interest for assistance services, based on the insight provided by the CHORIZO 'Insighter'	2,5,6	D2.2	M12	INLEIN (EV-ILVO)

**Note: The Responsible Partners were designated as a point of reference at the start of the project, specifically in month 6. However, as the project advanced, some changes have been made whenever it was deemed necessary for the benefit of the project when a different partner would be better suited to attain the desired outcome and/or with any changes in the due dates of certain deliverables.*

2.2 Criteria to assess the achievement of the results

“A criterion is a standard or principle used in evaluation as the basis for evaluative judgement” OECD, 2021)¹. Criteria are considered as “a set of lenses” that enable comprehension and analysis of an evaluated product/result/intervention etc. They also serve as a recognized framework for establishing an evaluation strategy, offering a comprehensive and systematic approach, and a common language that is utilized from the start of the evaluation procedure (OECD, 2021)¹. Moreover, by defining criteria, a distinct framework of desired or satisfactory results is laid out, which enables assessing the effectiveness of actions and choices taken, or procedures planned. Likewise, utilizing criteria for evaluation promotes a more informed and unbiased approach, that helps in the recognition of any gaps or deficiencies and also facilitates corrective actions or identification of areas that require improvement or further advancement (OECD, 2021)¹.

¹ OECD (2021), “The six criteria: Their purpose and role within evaluation”, in Applying Evaluation Criteria Thoughtfully, OECD Publishing, Paris

In this essence during the first six months of the project, CHORIZO has launched a set of assessment criteria, to (i) evaluate the performance/quality or success of the short-term results; (ii) to measure the extent to which short-term results have been achieved; and (iii) provide an objective evaluation of the achievements. The selected criteria were built using the corresponding Medium-term Outcomes of the project (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**) as “benchmarks”, since CHORIZO intends to accomplish the results outlined in the 'Results (short-term)' Column, with the expectation of surpassing them, thus enabling the achievement of the 'Outcomes (medium-term)' two years after the end of the project. The criteria established for the evaluation of each short-term result are described in Sections **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**, 2.2.4 and 0.

2.2.1 Assessment groups to evaluate the short-term results

There are two methods used to evaluate the short-term results (S-TR) of CHORIZO. The first involves the project consortium in the evaluation process and it is based on specific quantitative evaluation criteria. The second employs a broad participatory approach that involves external stakeholders (such as food actors, associations, and others), either to contribute to achieving the short-term result or to participate in the evaluation/assessment process (included in column “Assessment groups”). Table 3 shows whether the assessment for each short-term result is carried out by the Consortium alone or involves external stakeholders.

Table 3 Stakeholder engagement in achieving and evaluation of Short-term results

ID	Short-Term Result	INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (Consortium)	EXTERNAL INVOLVEMENT (Stakeholders)	Assessment groups
1	2 peer-reviewed articles, describing the evidence-based analysis results.	✓		Consortium Assessment
2	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the structure of the FLW index and its use in prioritising actions.	✓		Consortium Assessment
3	The sector-specific guidance is taken up by 1 food association to guide its members to better decision making.	✓	✓	Associations Engagement, Consortium Assessment
4	Acceptance of the CHORIZO Index by the EU FLW Prevention Hub team, as reference for prioritising actions.		✓	EU FLW Prevention Hub Engagement
5	The FLW actions’ database, is accessed by >200 food actors.	✓	✓	Food Actors Engagement, Consortium Assessment
6	Food actors that used the actions’ database, assessed its contribution to their decision making with an avg. rating of 5 (7-step Likert scale).		✓	Food Actors Assessment
7	6 peer-reviewed articles, presenting the interaction between social norms and FLW behaviour, based on the empirical data generated by the project (1 article per CS).	✓		Consortium Assessment
8	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the Integrated MOA - HUMAT modelling	✓		Consortium Assessment

ID	Short-Term Result	INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (Consortium)	EXTERNAL INVOLVEMENT (Stakeholders)	Assessment groups
	framework, and its deployment in the project.			
9	The FLW rapid appraisal tool, is accessed by >50 food actors.	✓	✓	Food Actors Engagement, Consortium Assessment
10	Food actors' assessment of the contribution of knowledge on social norms to their decision making (avg. rating: 5, in 7-step Likert scale).		✓	Food Actors Assessment
11	3 project articles to be provided as Open Access.	✓		Consortium Assessment
12	1 database of >300 previous FLW initiatives (classified into an FLW action taxonomy) to be provided as Open Access.	✓		Consortium Assessment
13	1 communication package (3 products) focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors.	✓	✓	Relevant actors Engagement, Consortium Assessment
14	1 science education package focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors.	✓	✓	Relevant actors Engagement, Consortium Assessment
15	Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 20% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused communication products, testified by the CS members (before vs after).	✓		Consortium Assessment
16	Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 25% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused science education package, testified by 2 schools (before vs after).	✓	✓	2 Schools Engagement, Consortium Assessment
17	Food actors' assessment of the influence that the project, communication, education & capacity building outputs, had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives (avg. rating: 4, in 7-step Likert scale).		✓	Food Actors Assessment
18	Adoption of the CHORIZO communication products by 2 consumer associations, 2 European FW-related Associations, and 3 Local Governments.	✓	✓	Consumer Associations, European FLW-related Associations, Local Governments Engagement,

ID	Short-Term Result	INTERNAL ASSESSMENT (Consortium)	EXTERNAL INVOLVEMENT (Stakeholders)	Assessment groups
19	Adoption of the CHORIZO science education package by 2 schools.	✓	✓	Consortium Assessment 2 Schools Engagement, Consortium Assessment
20	5 providers and consumers of empirical evidence, share data based on specific rules through the CHORIZO 'Insighter' Datahub.	✓		Data providers & consumers Engagement, Consortium Assessment
21	2 companies express their formal interest for assistance services, based on the insight provided by the CHORIZO 'Insighter'.	✓	✓	Companies Engagement, Consortium Assessment

In total, **8** short-term result achievements will be assessed by the CHORIZO Consortium without needing the engagement of external stakeholders due to their clear quantitative nature, **10** short-term result achievements will be assessed by the CHORIZO Consortium with the engagement of external stakeholders, and **3** will be assessed by external stakeholders.

2.2.2 Short-term results achievement classification

Classifying an achievement largely depends on the specific goal or objective one intends to achieve. In CHORIZO the aim is to assess through classification the extent to which the project has achieved its foreseen scientific, societal & economic/technological impacts. In this regard, classification pertains to the level of accomplishment or quality of short-term results and the degree to which such results have been attained.

Moreover, the achievement of the CHORIZO short-term results was classified based on:

- the FWCI of published articles to increase scientific impact (IDs: 1, 2, 7, 8).
- the adoption of specific results by external actors, that could result in their upscaling (IDs: 3, 4, 18, 19).
- the involvement of external actors to achieve wider impact in decision making and engagement in FLW initiatives (IDs: 5, 6, 9, 10, 13, 14, 17).
- publishing as Open Access to increase scientific contribution in the field (IDs: 11, 12).
- FLW reduction to increase environmental and societal impact (IDs: 15, 16).
- the Involvement of pertinent consumers and data providers to increase economic and technological impact (IDs: 20, 21).

In this regard, the performance of each achievement was evaluated based on a scale consisting of three classes: “good”, “very good”, and “excellent”, the definition of which is provided below.

- **Good:** The achievement is a positive outcome and contributes to a significant extent to the overall goals of the research project.
- **Very Good:** The achievement fully fulfils the initial goals of the research project and has the potential to make a significant contribution to the field.

- **Excellent:** This achievement demonstrates a very high degree of scientific and technological innovation / has an extremely significant impact on society and the environment / has a substantial potential for further research, adoption and impact.

2.2.3 Short-term results with Scientific Impact

ID 1: 2 peer-reviewed articles, describing the evidence-based analysis results

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
1	2 peer-reviewed articles, describing the evidence-based analysis results	1	D1.2	M10	Field-Weighted Citation Index (FWCI) > 1.3 per article.

Publishing 2 peer reviewed articles on the evidence-based analysis results (ID 1) is related to Deliverable 1.2 (M10). Two years after the end of the Project the FWCI of these articles should be greater than 1.3.

- If the articles are published early in the project, then FWCI index will be monitored as the project progresses.
- If the articles are published at the end of the Project, then we cannot monitor the progress due to time limits. In this case we can use the FWCI Index of the journal in the pertinent field, at the time of publication.

In any case, depending on the Index value, the achievement can be evaluated as follows:

0.5<FWCI<1	1<FWCI<1.2	1.2<FWCI< 1.3
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is partially achieved and the evaluation status is good.

The first article is based on D1.2 with the title “How Mobile Applications Can Address Food Waste-Related Behaviour at the Household Level” is planned to be submitted in “Sustainability” journal at the end of September 2025 as open access. Project partners VLTN and UCPH worked together to produce the paper, which explores how food waste interventions that incorporate applications at the household level are able to shape the drivers of food waste-related behaviour. The theoretical framework utilised in the paper to better understand the complexity of the multiple and interconnected factors that affect behaviour is the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) framework.

As the article has not been published yet, we will use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “Sustainability” has:

- Overall FWCI: 0.89 (median 0.09)
- Citations/publications: 11.6 (total citations: 337/ outputs:29)
- Open Access: 48.8%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 1.37

- Outputs in top 10%views: 44.8%

The journal offers solid visibility and engagement. Similarly, 11.6 citations/publications indicate consistent scholarly focus.

The second article is also based on D1.2 with the title “Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Solutions in Surplus Food Redistribution Efforts at the City Level” has been submitted in “Discover Sustainability” journal as open access and is under review. Project partners VLTN, ICLEI and ILVO have worked together to do the necessary conceptualization, literature review, data collection, analysis, and draft the article. which focuses on surplus food redistribution efforts at the municipal level within the EU, to uncover the prevalent challenges, coping mechanisms, and solutions in carrying out these initiatives within the broader context of addressing food waste.

As the article is under review, we will use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “Discover Sustainability” has:

- Overall FWCI: 0.95 (median 0.51)
- Yearly FWCI: 2021 0.28 / 2022 0.98 / 2023 0.65 / 2024 0.96
- Citations/publications: 6.5 (total citations: 4,547/ outputs:702)
- Open Access: 100%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 3.66
- Outputs in top 10%views: 61.3%

An overall FWCI of 0.95 indicates citation performance close to global average and the rest of the metrics indicate that the journal provides strong visibility and readers attention. On the same time, the citations/publications reveal strong publishing presence, with high reach and public engagement.

ID 2: 1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the structure of the FLW index and its use in prioritising actions

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
2	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the structure of the FLW index and its use in prioritising actions.	1	D1.3	M12	Article FWCI > 1.3

Publishing 1 peer-reviewed article on the structure of the FLW index and its use in prioritising actions (ID 2) is related to Deliverable 1.3 (M12). Two years after the end of the Project the FWCI of this article should be greater than 1.3.

- If the article is published early in the project, then FWCI index will be monitored as the project progresses.
- If the article is published at the end of the Project, then we cannot monitor the progress due to time limits. In this case we can use the FWCI Index of the journal in the pertinent field, at the time of publication.

In any case, depending on the Index value, the achievement can be evaluated as follows:

0.5<FWCI<1	1<FWCI<1.2	1.2<FWCI< 1.3
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and the evaluation status is almost good.

The article is based on D1.3 with title “Evaluation Methodologies to Assess Interventions Addressing Food Waste: A Review”, drafted by VLTN, and is to be published in “The International Journal of Sociology of Agriculture and Food” as open access. The main goal of the paper is to explore the methodologies to date utilised to assess interventions addressing food waste, highlight data gaps, potential future developments, and in particular inclusion in future assessments if the intervention addresses behaviour related to food waste generation.

As the article is under review, we will use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “The International Journal of Sociology of Agriculture and Food” has:

- Overall FWCI: 0.48 (median 0.26)
- Yearly FWCI: 2020 0.79 / 2021 0.59 / 2022 0.42 / 2023 0.32 / 2024 0.36
- Citations/publications: 3 (total citations: 160/ outputs: 54)
- Open Access: 0%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 0.85
- Outputs in top 10%views: 11.1%

This journal has a FWCI slightly lower than our evaluation as good, but it should be highlighted that it serves a highly specialised community. This can be observed from the small yearly output (54 for last four years) and the slow citation cycles which reduce the FW averages. The topic of the article is highly relevant for policy-oriented qualitative research and the journal connects directly with the intended audience.

ID 3: The sector-specific guidance is taken up by 1 food association to guide its members to better decision making

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
3	The sector-specific guidance is taken up by 1 food association to guide its members to better decision-making	1,5,6	D1.4	M15	The sector-specific guidance is taken up by 3 food association to guide its members’ decisions

The Sector Specific guidance is delivered in M15 through D1.4. Then, related food associations were approached with the aim to engage at least one to guide their members to better decision making. This result is directly linked to Task 5.4 that requires the engagement of “at least 4 FWA across EU with a view to their inputs, considerations, needs and requirements being clearly understood, in turn aligning the project’s outputs to address FWA adoption needs”. The assessment approach also probed for feedback by the Associations on their impression on the sector-specific guidance. E.g., *How did they find it? Was it useful/ helpful? Would they recommend it to other related associations?*

Taking into account that 2 years after the end of the Project it is expected that 3 Associations will take up the Sector-specific guidance; to guide their members, the achievement of the short-term result can be evaluated as follows:

1 Association	2 Associations	3 Associations
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is excellent.

Following the completion of the D1.4 “Sector specific guidance” the aim was to engage at least one company/association per sector and inform them of the content, usefulness and demonstrate its applicability for their relevant targeted sector. This process was carried out into three steps. First, the identification of the companies/associations that would benefit from the guidance. In a second step, CHORIZO partners contacted specific companies to share the sector-specific guidance. In third step the CHORIZO partners followed up to encourage participation and gather input.

Overall, 20 companies were identified and contacted from the consortium partners. As of this date, 9 have already replied positively and provided initial feedback. Below table shows the list and short comments received.

Table 4 List of companies/associations contacted for Sector-specific guidance

#	Companies/associations identified	Feedback	Sector - target audience
1	Tourism and Hospitality Chamber of Slovenia	Review the guidance for potential use in upcoming work.	Hospitality sector
2	Chamber of Agricultural and Food Enterprises	Recognized the potential of the document to support innovation and sustainability in the agri-food sector. Requested Slovenian version to share with more members. A Slovenian executive summary was developed and sent to them.	Agricultural companies and food processors
3	Chamber of Small Business and Trade	Further examination with a view to integrate in future activities.	Retail sector
4	Municipality Murska Sobota	Welcomed the document and identified several ideas applicable to local context. They expressed interest in further dissemination, subject to translation.	Municipality
5	Ministry of agriculture, forestry and food.	Expressed appreciation and noted the relevance to the Slovenian context, especially for fostering cooperation with municipalities. Inquired for availability of a Slovenian version and indicated their willingness to publish it on their website. The proposed actively promoting the recommendations to local mayors, the Chamber of Craft and Small Business, and the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry, including presenting concrete examples of potential collaboration and	Ministry

		actions. A Slovenian executive summary was developed and sent to them.	
6	Slovenian Advisory Service for farming	Appreciated the practical value of the recommendations, noting their relevance for farmers and rural development. They indicated interest in sharing the content more widely if translated.	Farmers
7	The Future in Our Hand	Responded interested and grateful that we are trying to make our research have an actual practical impact. They will review and share with colleagues working on FW.	Environmental and solidarity organizations
8	FEBA	An online session specifically tailored for food banks was held on 27 June to present and discuss the guidance document.	European Food Banks Federation
9	Hungarian FLW Platform	Main findings of the guidance, particularly those relevant to food chain stakeholders, will be presented at the OMEK food fair in Budapest on 18th of September.	Sectorial organisations, government and academic institutions, companies and NGOs present (~50 members)

Other companies/associations contacted but have not received feedback yet are:

BEUC (The European Consumer Organization), COPA-COGECA (European farmers and agricultural cooperatives), International Food Waste Coalition (food services sector), Norwegian Food bank (network of food banks), Matvett (food and hospitality industry's initiative (businesses, authorities, and research communities)), Melk (agricultural information office), Matprat, Voorlichtingsbureau voor Eieren en Vlees, Voorlichtingsbureau voor Brood en Graan (well-known Norwegian recipe website), Mattilsynet (Government agency and directorate), Cooperativas Agroalimentarias de España (Primary production), 45 FIAB associations and FoodDrinkEurope (Food processing and manufacturing all Spanish food sectors represented), FoodforLife (whole supply chain).

Overall, the response on the sector-specific guidance is positive and it indicates that it is perceived as practical, relevant and applicable in various contexts and real-life application.

ID 4: Acceptance of the CHORIZO Index by the EU FLW Prevention Hub team, as reference for prioritising actions

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
4	Acceptance of the CHORIZO Index by the EU FLW Prevention Hub team as reference for prioritising actions	1,6	D1.3	M12	The Index is embedded in the sustainability reports of 5 organisations to guide FLW initiatives

The CHORIZO FLW Index is delivered in Month 12 through D1.3. One of the main goals of the project is to take all the required measures to ensure that the Index will be recognized by the EU FLW

Prevention Hub team as a point of reference for determining which actions to prioritize. Following that, it is anticipated that two years following the conclusion of CHORIZO, the Index will be integrated into the sustainability reports of five organizations to provide guidance for their FLW initiatives.

For the assessment of this short-term result, CHORIZO will respond to the following question:

- Acceptance of the CHORIZO Index by the EU FLW Prevention Hub team, as reference for prioritising actions.

ASSESSMENT:

The short-term result has been achieved. In April 2025, a synthesis document focusing solely on the methodology used for the indices was accepted and uploaded onto the FLW Hub (under "Resources") and included also in the Hub's May newsletter.

It is important to note that the acceptance as a reference tool for prioritising actions, validates the methodology used and helps transferring the project findings into relevant policy channels. The synthesis document was reviewed by the FLW Hub before uploading it onto its respective website as a resource.

It is unknown to date if the index is already embedded in the sustainability report of an organization, this will be monitored as part of the follow-up activities to assess medium-term uptake.

ID 5: The FLW actions’ database, is accessed by >200 food actors

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
5	The FLW actions’ database, is accessed by >200 food actors	1	D1.2	M10	The FLW actions’ database, is accessed by >500 food actors

The Actions database is delivered in month 10 through Deliverable 1.2. To assess the achievement of this short-term result, we also consider the corresponding expected medium-term outcome, which is that the FLW actions database will be accessed by >500 food actors. In this regard, the assessment will be based on the number of the actors that have accessed the database.

DB accessed by 200-250 actors	DB accessed by 250-300 actors	DB accessed by >300 actors
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is excellent.

As of August 2025, the datahub monitoring tool recorded 6,433 page views with 5,667 unique page views.

From a qualitative point of view, the survey which pops up in the datahub confirms that the stakeholders engaging with it represent a wide spectrum of the food supply chain. The indicated

areas from the respondents are communication, food service, consumer engagement, customer-facing activities, research, industry and cross-project collaboration (for example ZeroW project).

The high level of web traffic in combination with the diverse user base shows its relevance and impact across the food system. Thus, making it a valuable resource for guiding future actions and decision making.

ID 6: Food actors that used the actions’ database, assessed its contribution to their decision making with an avg. rating of 5 (7-step Likert scale)

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
6	Food actors that used the actions’ database, assessed its contribution to their decision making with an avg. rating of 5 (7-step Likert scale)	1	D1.2	M10	Food actors that used the actions’ database, assessed its contribution to their decision making with an avg. rating of 6 (7-step Likert scale)

This short-term result also depended on the Actions’ database (D1.2, M10). In this case the engaged actors had to rate the database’s contribution in their decision making using a 7-step Likert scale. The achievement will be considered successful if it is rated with at least an average rating of 5. But if we also consider the corresponding Medium-term Outcome, which is “Food actors that used the actions’ database, assessed its contribution to their decision making with an avg. rating of 6”, the assessment can be classified as follows:

Average rating <5	5<avg. rating<6	6<avg. rating<7
Corrective actions/revision needed	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is very good.

As part of WP4 and the capacity building programme implemented by partner CSCP, there was a post-survey questionnaire which was given to the participants after the workshops and webinars. A question concerning the Actions’ database was incorporated into the post-survey, asking respondents to indicate in accordance with the Likert scale to which extent the database contributed to their decision making in their work. The results of the survey regarding the relevance for decision making, was an average score of 5.4 and a median score of 5.5.

A similar survey was conducted to other users, most of whom rated the contribution positively, with the vast majority selecting “Agree”. The average score is 5.7 and median 6, very few respondents were neutral and no one disagreed. This result confirms that the actions databased is perceived as useful and highly relevant to decision making.

ID 7: 6 peer-reviewed articles, presenting the interaction between social norms and FLW behaviour, based on the empirical data generated by the project (1 article per CS)

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
7	6 peer-reviewed articles, presenting the interaction between social norms and FLW behaviour, based on the empirical data generated by the project (1 article per CS)	2	D2.3	M18	FWCI > 1.3 per article

Publishing 6 peer reviewed articles to present the interaction between social norms and FLW behaviour (1 article per CS) is related to D2.3 (M18). Two years after the end of the Project the FWCI of these articles should be greater than 1.3.

- If the articles are published early in the project, then FWCI index will be monitored as the project progresses.
- If the articles are published at the end of the Project, then we cannot monitor the progress due to time limits. In this case we can use the FWCI Index of the journal in the pertinent field, at the time of publication.

In any case, depending on the Index value, the achievement can be evaluated as follows:

0.5<FWCI<1	1<FWCI<1.2	1.2<FWCI< 1.3
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is partially achieved for numbers 2 and 5 the evaluation status for is excellent and good respectively. Numbers 1, 3, 4 and 6 will be published after the end of the project.

1. The article based on CS1 and Belgium survey data with title “Investigating the impact of social norms and uncertainty on household food waste, the case of Flanders-Belgium” is planned to be published end of September 2025. The main goal of the paper is improving knowledge by providing insights into uncertainty and identity behaviours of consumers at household level and the social norms influencing FW at Flemish households and building upon various analyses from D2.3.
2. The article based on CS1 and the Belgium and Spain survey data with the title “Wasting Despite Motivation: Exploring the Impact of Abilities and Difficulty on Food Waste Behavior Through Brehm’s Motivation Intensity Theory” has been submitted in “Foods” journal on the 7th of August 2025 as open access. This is a complementary paper to the first one, but it is based on psychological theories and a larger sample (Flanders and Spain).

As the article was accepted on the 25th of September, we will use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “Foods” has:

- Overall FWCI: 1.55 (median 1.22)
- Yearly FWCI: 2020 1.71 / 2021 1.56 / 2022 1.58 / 2023 1.52 / 2024 1.47

- Citations/publications: 15.7 (total citations: 280,950 / outputs: 17,877)
- Open Access: 100%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 1.52
- Outputs in top 10%views: 24.7%

The evaluation status is excellent as there is an above-average FWCI (~1.5) across all the years. This journal has a very high volume of citations and is fully Open Access. In parallel we observe strong engagement indicators, which in combination with the high citation density denotes a strong channel for visibility and uptake.

3. The article based on a field experiment at a hotel buffet in Norway (CS2) with title “Shaping Choices: The Impact of Message Framing on Food Waste Behavior in Hotel Buffets” was ready to be submitted in “Nature Communication” journal but after some new information received on the 15th of September 2025 from a former employee, it is necessary to recompute the data. Therefore, the submission will be after the end of the project and the intention is to publish open access, but this will also depend on the open-access fees of the journal. The main goal of the paper is improving knowledge on how to frame communication in order to be effective to evoke needed behavioral change.

As the article is under review, we will use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “Nature Communication” has:

- Overall FWCI: 2.87 (median 1.79)
- Yearly FWCI: 2020 3.07 / 2021 2.97 / 2022 2.99 / 2023 2.84 / 2024 2.62
- Citations/publications: 43.1 (total citations: 1,779,827 / outputs: 41,273)
- Open Access: 100%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 1.98
- Outputs in top 10%views: 39%

The evaluation status is excellent as the journal has a very high FWCI (~2.6-3.1) every year. This top-tier journal has a substantial volume of citations and is fully Open Access. It offers exceptional visibility and strong reach and widespread use.

4. The article based on CS4 (focus group with students) and the educational board game on FW (T4.3) with title “Utilizing Gamification to Enhance Intergenerational Communication Dynamics Among Pupils, and Schoolteachers on Food Waste Literacy Among School Children to behavioral change related to social norms” is planned to be submitted to the “Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior or Youth” on the 15th of November as open access. The main goal of the paper is providing insights on the role of gamification for Food Waste literacy for the school kids.

If the article is finally submitted in this journal, we can use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the “Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior or Youth” has:

- Overall FWCI: 0.62 (median 0.42)
- Yearly FWCI: 2020 0.59 / 2021 0.64 / 2022 0.69 / 2023 0.56 / 2024 0.63
- Citations/publications: 6.1 (total citations: 4,214 / outputs: 692)
- Open Access: 47.98%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 0.92
- Outputs in top 10%views: 6.4%

The evaluation result for this journal is good, in this established journal with a consistent publishing schedule that reaches a clear audience in nutrition education, public health and

behavior change practices. This makes it a strong channel for not only academic impact, but also actual use of the findings in programmes, guidance and teaching. The relatively high share of Open Access will also support wider reach and community reuse within the intended target audience.

5. The article based on CS3 (Consumer survey data in Slovenia) with title “An Exploratory Analysis of Consumer Attitudes and Behavioral Intentions Toward Food Waste Reduction in Slovenian Food Services” has been published in “Sustainability” journal in April 2025 (Volume 17, Issue 9, Article 3953) as open access. The main goal of the paper is providing insights into Slovenian consumers’ attitudes and behavioural intentions toward food waste reduction strategies in the food service sector.

As the article was published recently, we will use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “Sustainability” has:

- Overall FWCI: 0.89 (median 0.09)
- Citations/publications: 11.6 (total citations: 337/ outputs:29)
- Open Access: 48.8%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 1.37
- Outputs in top 10%views: 44.8%

The evaluation status is good and the journal offers solid visibility, engagement and consistent scholarly focus.

6. The article based on CS5 interviews with title “AI-Assisted Qualitative Research: Enhancing Human Interpretation through topic-guided Large Language Models in Multi-Stakeholder Interview Analysis.” is planned to be submitted in “International Journal of Qualitative Methods” journal during Q1 2026. The main goal of the paper is exploring the collaborative potential of Natural Language Processing (NLP) with qualitative research methods to enhance efficiency and depth in thematic analysis, focusing on food waste. The topic modelling with data has been finalised but additional analysis with blind review of hybrid- and AI- generated reports is required.

If the article is finally submitted in this journal, we can use the journal level FWCI for the 2020-2024 window, where the journal “The International Journal of Qualitative Methods” has:

- Overall FWCI: 2.05 (median 0.77)
- Yearly FWCI: 2020 3.38 / 2021 2.11 / 2022 1.79 / 2023 1.94 / 2024 1.55
- Citations/publications: 17.3 (total citations: 17,441/ outputs: 1,008)
- Open Access: 96.03%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 0.54
- Outputs in top 10%views: 5.8%

This large and active journal has a FWCI which has been consistently above average (more than 1.5) since 2020. It also has a very high Open Access availability and strong citation density which indicates growing interest and use within qualitative methods communities.

ID 8: 1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the Integrated MOA - HUMAT modelling framework, and its deployment in the project

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
8	1 peer-reviewed article, presenting the Integrated MOA - HUMAT modelling framework, and its deployment in the project	3	D3.1	M11	Article FWCI > 1.3

Publishing 1 peer reviewed article to present the Integrated MOA - HUMAT modelling framework, and its deployment in the project is related to Deliverable 3.1 (M11). Two years after the end of the Project the FWCI of these articles should be greater than 1.3.

- If the article is published early in the project, then FWCI index will be monitored as the project progresses.
- If the article is published at the end of the Project, then we cannot monitor the progress due to time limits. In this case we can use the FWCI Index of the journal in the pertinent field, at the time of publication.

In any case, depending on the Index value, the achievement can be evaluated as follows:

0.5<FWCI<1	1<FWCI<1.2	1.2<FWCI< 1.3
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation is excellent.

Based on CS2 data from the experiments in Strawberry hotels in Norway with title “To Eat or Not to Eat: Modeling Food Loss and Waste Behavior at a Hotel Breakfast Buffet” has been published in “Cleaner and Responsible Consumption Journal” in September 2025. The main goal of the paper is understanding how motivations, opportunities, abilities, and social norms collectively impact food waste behavior in a buffet setting. This is done by developing, calibrating and validating an agent-based model that realistically represents individual food waste behavior in a commercial setting, in particular at a hotel breakfast buffet. The model integrates the HUMAT framework - a socio-cognitive architecture for decision-making - along with the MOA framework, which represents motivations, opportunities, and abilities, as well as social norms that influence food-related choices like meal timing, portion sizes, and leftovers. The model is calibrated and validated by using empirical data from experiments conducted at Strawberry Hotels in Norway.

The journal “Cleaner and Responsible Consumption Journal” (2020-2024) has:

- Overall FWCI: 1.6 (median 1.05)
- Yearly FWCI: 2020 0.9 / 2021 1.45 / 2022 1.09 / 2023 1.95 / 2024 1.72
- Citations/publications: 13.5 (total citations: 3,180/ outputs: 236)
- Open Access: 98.31%
- Field-Weighted View Impact (FWVI): 2.98

- Outputs in top 10%views: 74.2%

This journal shows strong citation impact 1.6, with more than 1.3 in the recent years. The visibility indicators are high, it has many citations along with the near-universal open access, it provides a robust context for adoption.

ID 9: The FLW rapid appraisal tool, is accessed by >50 food actors

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
9	The FLW rapid appraisal tool, is accessed by >50 food actors	3,6	D3.5	M34	The FLW actions’ database, is accessed by >100 food actors

The OFLW Visualizer/Rapid appraisal tool will be delivered in Month 33, through Deliverable 3.5. CHORIZO should provide access to >50 food actors by the end of the project. To assess the achievement of this short-term result, we consider as a benchmark the corresponding Medium-term Outcome (*the FLW rapid appraisal tool is accessed by >100 food actors*) that is expected to be accomplished 2 years after the project. In this regard, the assessment will be based on the number of the actors that have accessed the rapid appraisal tool.

Tool accessed by 50-70 actors	Tool accessed by 70-100 actors	Tool accessed by >100 actors
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is good.

UNIBO developed a demo version of the OFLW Visualizer/Rapid appraisal tool for use during Capacity Building phase (M28-M32). CSCP shared it using the capacity building. As part of WP4 and the capacity building programme, there is a post-survey questionnaire which is given to the participants after the workshops and webinars. A question concerning the use of the rapid appraisal tool has been incorporated into the post-survey.

“Of the 8 respondents who evaluated the Visualizer, the tool received an average score of 6, with a median of 6.5, in response to the question of whether it would be helpful for food waste-related decision making. This reflects a strong perceived potential for the tool to support informed choices in this area. When asked whether they would consider using the Visualizer to reduce food loss and waste within their organisation, the responses were slightly more reserved, with both the average and median scores at 5.5. This suggests that while the tool’s usefulness is broadly acknowledged, its actual integration into organisational processes may depend on further familiarisation or context-specific needs” (from the analysis of the capacity-building questionnaire results, more details in D4.4 Capacity building and Help desk).

The final version of the tool has been presented at the Final Conference the 16th of September and at the Coffee Talks from WASTELESS project the 19th of September. During these events, feedback was collected through a short survey, which received 58 responses. While this already exceeds the project’s target of 50 food system actors, it is reasonable to assume that the actual number of users who explored the tool is even higher, as not all participants may have completed the questionnaire.

We evaluated the OFLW Visualizer/Rapid Appraisal Tool across 3 dimensions: usefulness, likelihood of future use, recommendation to others.

The survey results indicate a generally positive reception of the Visualizer across all three dimensions evaluated.

- Usefulness: A majority of respondents rated the tool positively, with 81% giving it a score of 7 or higher. The most common ratings were 8 (20 people) and 9 (15 people), suggesting that users find the Visualizer both helpful and relevant to their work.
- Likelihood of future use: Responses were slightly more distributed but still encouraging. About 77% of participants rated their likelihood of using the tool at 7 or above, with peaks at 7 (15 people), 8 (12 people), and 10 (10 people). This indicates solid potential for continued and practical adoption.
- Recommendation to others: This was the most positive indicator. 71% rated 8 or higher, with 17 respondents giving the maximum score of 10. This suggests strong word-of-mouth potential and credibility of the tool among food actors.

Overall, the feedback confirms that the Visualizer is seen as a useful and user-friendly resource, with good prospects for adoption and dissemination beyond the initial group of users.

ID 10: Food actors’ assessment of the contribution of knowledge on social norms to their decision making (avg. rating: 5, in 7-step Likert scale)

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
10	Food actors’ assessment of the contribution of knowledge on social norms to their decision making (avg. rating: 5, in 7-step Likert scale)	3,6	D3.5	M34	Food actors’ assessment of the contribution of social norms’ knowledge to their decision making (avg. rating: 6, in 7-step Likert scale)

This short-term result depends on the knowledge gained in CHORIZO on social norms (D3.5, M33). In this case, as in short term result ID 6, the engaged food actors will have to rate this knowledge contribution in their decision making using a 7-step Likert scale. The achievement will be considered successful if it is rated with at least an average rating of 5. But if we also consider the corresponding Medium-term Outcome, which is “Food actors’ assessment of the contribution of social norms’ knowledge to their decision making (avg. rating: 6, in 7-step Likert scale)”, the assessment can be classified as follows:

Average rating <5	5<avg. rating<6	6<avg. rating<7
corrective actions/revision needed	very good	excellent

ASSESEMENT:

The result is completed and evaluation status is very good/excellent.

As part of WP4 and the capacity building programme implemented by partner CSCP, a post-survey questionnaire was given to the participants after the workshops and webinars. A question concerning the knowledge of social norms contributing to the decision making has been incorporated into the post-survey. A summary of the results from the analysis of the capacity-building questionnaire results (more details in D4.4 Capacity building and Help desk) in relation to each tool is presented below and their role in advancing knowledge and guiding decision making.

Capacity Building General

“All respondents gave a rating of 5 or higher, with a median response of 6, which infers a high quality perception of the Capacity Building sessions of the first segment.”

Datahub

“When asked whether the DataHub will provide solutions to reduce food loss and waste (FLW) within their organisation, the average score was 5.8, with a median of 6. Concerning the question regarding the DataHub’s relevance for organisational decision making, the average score was 5.4 with a median of 5.5. These slightly more cautious evaluations were attributed by respondents to a current lack of familiarity with the full range of available content or a need for more practical exposure before assessing the tool’s impact on decision making.”

During the second survey, as already indicated in ID6, most of the participants rated the contribution positively, with an average score of 5.7 and median 6, very few respondents were neutral and no one disagreed.

These results confirm that the datahub is perceived as useful, highly relevant to decision making and its potential can grow after a period of use and learning.

Visualizer

“Of the 8 respondents who evaluated the Visualizer, the tool received an average score of 6, with a median of 6.5, in response to the question of whether it would be helpful for food waste-related decision making. This reflects a strong perceived potential for the tool to support informed choices in this area. When asked whether they would consider using the Visualizer to reduce food loss and waste within their organisation, the responses were slightly more reserved, with both the average and median scores at 5.5. This suggests that while the tool’s usefulness is broadly acknowledged, its actual integration into organisational processes may depend on further familiarisation or context-specific needs.”

On the Visualizer survey, most participants found the tool helpful, with an average rating of 5.6 and a median rating 6 (Agree). While 65% of respondents selected “Agree” or higher, a few were neutral or slightly disagreed. This shows that the tool can improve its relevance for certain user groups. This has been taken into account and the future plans of the Visualizer include the addition of more examples and practical use cases.

Overall, the food actors see a clear potential to the Visualizer’s potential to inform decision making and further improvements will support its use by a bigger variety of organisations.

Helpdesk

“Of the 5 respondents, who indicated interest in the CHORIZO Helpdesk, the average score was 5.6 and the median was 6 in response to the question whether they consider making use of the Helpdesk function to reduce food waste in their organisation.”

Generally speaking, some participants expressed optimism about the usefulness of the tools once they had more time to engage with them.

ID 11: 3 project articles to be provided as Open Access

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
11	3 project articles to be provided as Open Access	1, 2, 3, 4	various	M1-36	1 additional project article to be provided Open Access

This short-term result focuses on publishing as Open Access 3 project articles by the end of the project. WPs 1, 2, 3 and 4 are the WPs that might publish articles. In this case, if the medium-term Outcome for this short-term result is taken into consideration, the assessment of the achievement can be classified as follows:

3 articles as Open Access	4 articles as Open Access	5 articles as Open Access
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is excellent.

These articles were published as open access:

- ID1 – 2. “Challenges, Coping Mechanisms, and Solutions in Surplus Food Redistribution Efforts at the City Level”
- ID2 - “Evaluation Methodologies to Assess Interventions Addressing Food Waste: A Review”
- ID8 – “To Eat or Not to Eat: Modeling Food Loss and Waste Behavior at a Hotel Breakfast Buffet”
- ID7 – 2. “Wasting Despite Motivation: Exploring the Impact of Abilities and Difficulty on Food Waste Behavior Through Brehm’s Motivation Intensity Theory”
- ID7 – 5. “An Exploratory Analysis of Consumer Attitudes and Behavioral Intentions Toward Food Waste Reduction in Slovenian Food Services”

ID 12: 1 database of >300 previous FLW initiatives (classified into an FLW action taxonomy) to be provided as Open Access

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
12	1 database of >300 previous FLW initiatives (classified into an FLW action taxonomy) to be provided as Open Access	1	D1.2	M10	Expansion of the database (>400 initiatives)

The Actions database of >300 previous FLW initiatives was delivered in month 10 through D1.2. In accordance with Open Access, the database of actions is freely accessible to the public via the project’s public website at: <https://chorizoproject.eu/deliverables-repository/>. In addition, it should

be considered if the corresponding short-term result of >300 actions were identified during the course of the project. In this regard, the assessment will be based on the number of the initiatives included in the database:

300>initiatives>330	330<initiatives<350	initiatives>350
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and the evaluation status is excellent.

The list of interventions included in D1.2 “Evidence-based analysis of FLW actions/tools” have been uploaded to the Chorizo datahub in October 2023 with 395 identified actions across the European Union.

ID 13: 1 communication package (3 products) focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors.

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
13	1 communication package (3 products) focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors	4, 6	D4.2	M36	Revision of the communication package to include results from its adoption in new cases (see Impact 4)

The communication package focused on changing social norms will be delivered in month 36, through Deliverable 4.2. To assess the achievement of this short-term result, we will be based on the number of the actors with which the package will be shared. Besides, 2 years after the end of the project, the corresponding medium-term Outcome is to revise the package and include results from its adoption in new cases. Put differently, the greater the number of actors who can utilize the package, the higher the number of instances where it can be adopted, resulting in a higher number of results that can be included into the revised communication package.

50-70 relevant actors	70-100 relevant actors	>100 relevant actors
good	very good	excellent

It would be also interesting to collect information from the actors. E.g., What kind of actors accessed the tool? What was their impression? Feedback on that would be useful. E.g., Did they like it?

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is very good.

The scope of this result was expanded to produce a total of five standalone communication products. These products were then developed and refined with the CHORIZO partners and will be later tested and validated by the CSs.

Each communication product was designed for a specific target group making sure it was relevant and applicable to each of them. Here is the list:

- Relevant for Households (on Zero-Waste Host)
- Relevant for Hotels (portion size on Buffet Guest)
- Relevant for Food banks (Guidance pamphlet for ambassadors)
- Relevant for Foodservice kitchens or foodbanks (Donation decision tree)
- Relevant for Food industry (USE-BY vs BEST-BEFORE date labeling)

In order to assess the achievement of this result, the products were shared with relevant actors and their feedback was collected through a questionnaire. For more details, D4.2 includes the steps and analysis. A total of 74 fully completed and high-quality responses were received.

Concerning the response distribution, as shown below, the households obtained the highest engagement with quite a difference, confirming that communication tailored to citizens is what delivers the most significant impact and is considered highly relevant.

In addition, a Compendium of communication messages has been developed, taking into account cities as a user or facilitator of the communication products. The Compendium includes all five communication products, along with suggestions for how the Cities can use these communication products across different sectors and situations. This makes it possible to extend its use to a wider audience and maximises its adoption beyond the initial survey group.

ID 14: 1 science education package focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
14	1 science education package focused on changing social norms, shared with relevant actors	4,6	D4.3	M36	Revision of the science education package to include results from its adoption in new cases (see Impact 4)

The science education package focused on changing social norms will be delivered in month 36 through D4.3. To assess the achievement of this short-term result, we will be based on the number of the actors with which the package will be shared. Besides, 2 years after the end of the project, the corresponding medium-term Outcome is to revise the package to include results from its adoption in new cases. In this essence, the more actors that have access to the package, the more adoption cases, thus the more results to be included in the revised communication package.

50-70 relevant actors	70-100 relevant actors	>100 relevant actors
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is completed and evaluation status is excellent.

The education package includes teaching material for school teachers focused on food waste reduction related activity (“Hack your school lunch”) and a FW and educational board game. The prototype was tested by case schools to provide feedback as well as part of the validation process of the materials. The educational package was taken as useful for FW and food literacy education for school environment. However, it was suggested to incorporate element of gamification and fun element to enhance engagement.

The science educational products (FW and educational Board Game) have been shared with total of about 120 students from five schools across Europe (Germany, Austria, Spain and Denmark). Two schools in Denmark were the ones used for the case studies and ICLEI coordinated the board game to be piloted by the following 3 schools: Bremen, Germany: Verbraucherzentrale Bremen e.V. and Oberschule Rockwinkel, Vienna, Austria: Hannah Tögel, All-day Primary School Campus Donauefeld and Zaragoza, Spain: Victor Roda, Juan de Lanuza School and Mensa Civica.

Each school has provided feedback on the educational package, which were mostly positive, with some suggestions for improving the materials. The improvement suggestion was mostly on making content simpler and make use of graphic as much as possible.

Another educational product (teaching material for school teacher) has been shared with two school teachers from the case schools in Denmark. The suggestions included to make the learning process simpler and content shorter and clear. The feedback was amended, and the material was upgraded and conformed with the teachers.

2.2.4 Short-term results with Societal Impact

ID 15: Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 20% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused communication products, testified by the CS members (before vs after)

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
15	Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 20% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused communication products, testified by the CS members (before vs after)	4	D4.2	M36	25% FLW reduction, as a combined result of social norms change and better informed FLW actions’ selection (actions’ database)

The Social norms focused communication products will be delivered in M36 through D4.2. After testing them in the CS, it is expected that FLW will be reduced about 20% considering that behavioural change will be initiated.

For the assessment of this short-term result, CHORIZO will respond in the following questions:

Have the Social norms focused communication products reduced the FLW production? How much? Taking into consideration that 2 years after the end of the project the FLW reduction should be raised by 25% (Medium-term Outcome), the assessment of this achievement may be classified as follows:

20%<reduction<22%	23%<reduction<24%	reduction >25%
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is completed and evaluation status is very good.

Complete qualitative assessment of behavioural change resulting from the use of social norms-focused communication products was not feasible due to the time constraint, as it would have required an experimental setup. However, as a part of the validation process of the communication products, a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessment was conducted through the survey. The survey responses from the user group – potential users of the communication product – indicate that, on average, 80% of respondents expressed an intention to adapt the products and believed they could effectively guide the target audience in reducing food waste. Responses to the baseline questions regarding user group characteristics indicate that they possess a certain level of awareness about reducing food waste. More detailed presentation of the survey results can be found in related CHORIZO Deliverable (D4.2).

In addition, the communication products will also be presented with actors from local government through the City Interest groups on the 25th of September 2025.

ID 16: Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 25% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused science education package, testified by 2 schools (before vs after)

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
16	Evidence of behavioural change initiation leading to an estimated 25% FLW reduction, as a result of the social norms-focused science education package, testified by 2 schools (before vs after)	4	D4.3	M36	35% FLW reduction at schools, as a combined result of social norms' change and better informed FLW actions' selection (actions' database)

The Social norms-focused science education package will be delivered in M36 through D4.3. After testing them in at least 2 schools, it is expected that FLW will be reduced of about 25% considering that behavioural change will be initiated.

For the assessment of this short-term result, CHORIZO will respond in the following questions:

Has the Social norms-focused science education package reduced the FLW production? How much? Taking into consideration that 2 years after the end of the project the FLW reduction should be

raised by 35% (Medium-term Outcome), the assessment of this achievement may be classified as follows:

25%<reduction<27%	28%<reduction<29%	reduction >30%
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is completed and evaluation status is very good.

Similar to assessment on communication products (ID 15), complete qualitative assessment of behavioural change resulting from the use of social norms-focused educational package was not feasible due to the time constraint, as it would have required an experimental setup. However, as a part of the validation process of the educational products, a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessment of the FW and educational board game was conducted through the survey. The survey conducted across five schools in Europe yielded a total of 34 student responses, along with feedback from teachers. The average of 60% students thinks that the board game is easy to understand, a good tool for learning, enjoy playing the game and can relate the situation with their daily life. This suggests a strong potential for reducing food waste as students improve their food literacy through engaging to play the game in a school setting. More detailed presentation of the survey results can be found in related CHORIZO D4.3.

In addition to the educational board game, the teaching material for teacher (Hack Your School Food) is co-developed together with schoolteacher from two Danish schools. ICLEI also coordinated the Hack Your School Food educational material to be reviewed by two Germany-based educators. Teacher feedback indicates that the materials are useful for schools and have the potential to enhance students' food literacy, ultimately contributing to reduced food waste.

ID 17: Food actors’ assessment of the influence that the project, communication, education & capacity building outputs, had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives (avg. rating: 4, in 7-step Likert scale)

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
17	Food actors’ assessment of the influence that the project, communication, education & capacity building outputs, had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives (avg. rating: 4, in 7-step Likert scale)	4,6	D4.4	M35	Food actors’ assessment of the influence that the project, communication, education & capacity building outputs, had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives (avg. rating: 5, in 7-step Likert scale)

This short-term result depends on the delivery of communication, education & capacity building outputs (D4.4, M35). In this case the engaged food actors will have to rate the influence that the products had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives, using a 7-step Likert scale. The achievement will be considered successful if it is rated with at least an average rating of 4. But if we also consider the corresponding Medium-term Outcome, which is “Food actors’ assessment of the

influence that the project, communication, education & capacity building outputs, had on increasing their engagement in FLW initiatives (avg. rating: 5, in 7-step Likert scale)”, the assessment can be classified as follows:

4<avg. rating	4<avg. rating<5	avg. rating>5
corrective actions/revision needed	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is excellent.

According to our survey, the results show that the communication products are well perceived, with most of the respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that these channels have increased their engagement in FLW initiatives. This was rated with an average of 5.8 and a median of 6 and confirms that the communication strategy was successful in motivating the food actors and strengthening their engagement.

ID 18: Adoption of the CHORIZO communication products by 2 consumer associations, 2 European FW-related Associations, and 3 Local Governments

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
18	Adoption of the CHORIZO communication products by 2 consumer associations, 2 European FW-related Associations, and 3 Local Governments	4,6	D4.2	M36	Adoption of the CHORIZO communication products by 5 consumer associations, 5 European FW-related Associations, and 10 Local Governments

The CHORIZO communication products will be delivered in M36 through D4.2. Then, related consumer associations will be approached with the aim to engage at least 2 consumer associations, 2 European FW-related Associations, and 3 Local Governments to adopt them. This result is directly linked to Task 5.4 that requires the engagement of “at least 4 FWA across EU with a view to their inputs, consideration, needs and requirements being clearly understood, in turn aligning the project’s outputs to address FWA adoption needs”.

Considering that 2 years after the end of the Project (medium-term outcome) it is expected that 5 consumer associations, 5 European FW-related Associations, and 10 Local Governments will adopt the CHORIZO communication products, the achievement of the short-term result can be evaluated as follows:

2 consumer Associations 2 European FW-related Associations 3 Local Governments	3 consumer Associations 3 European FW-related Associations 4-5 Local Governments	4-5 consumer Associations 4-5 European FW-related Associations 6-10 Local Governments
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is partially achieved as the communication products were successfully shared with multiple organisations and initiatives and their potential adoption is still in progress. It is also important to mention that the final communication products, revised after the first feedback loop, were finalised in July, which allowed a one-month window for dissemination until the end of the project.

The communication products (relevant for households) were shared in the public event by project partner (CNTA), see the photos below (more pics available). The partner CNTA has also highlighted the communication products in their online community with consumers (Mundo Sabor) as practical resources to be used to reduce waste at home (<https://mundosabor.es/blog/el-proyecto-chorizo-llega-a-su-fin-gracias-por-acompanarnos-en-este-camino/>).

Figure 2 Photos from consumer facing event on home communication products

The City - Compendium of message and product target to various sectors and target groups was shared with cities through City Interest Group network, featuring 14 cities, through a webinar at the beginning of September 2025.

Finally, the communication products were shared with the European Union initiatives (EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste, EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub, European Environmental Bureau, EIP-AGRI Project Database), NGOs (Feedback EU, Slow Food Europe), Industry Alliances (FoodDrinkEurope, European Federation of Food Banks, Association of Manufacturers and Retailers) and National Authorities (Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food in Spain, Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food in Slovenia). More details can be found in the D5.4 Sustainability Strategy EU Food Waste Associations.

ID 19: Adoption of the CHORIZO science education package by 2 schools

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
19	Adoption of the CHORIZO science education package by 2 schools	4,6	D4.3	M36	Adoption of the CHORIZO science education package by 10 schools

The CHORIZO science education package will be delivered in M36 through D4.3. Then, schools will be approached with the aim to engage at least 2 to adopt them. It would be interesting if the approached schools provided feedback on their impression on the science education package. E.g., *How did they find it? Do they find it useful/helpful? Would they recommend it to other schools?*

Considering that 2 years after the end of the Project (medium-term outcome) it is expected that 10 schools will adopt the CHORIZO science education package, the achievement of this short-term result can be evaluated as follows:

2 Schools	3 -5 Schools	Schools >5
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is very good.

As also described in ID16, the Science Educations packages (FW and Educational Board Game) were tested and feedback was provided by a total of 5 schools from Spain (1), Germany (1), Austria (1), and Denmark (2). The testing in the three schools in Spain, Germany, and Austria, was conducted in collaboration with the ICLEI network and a more detailed presentation of the survey results can be found in related CHORIZO Deliverable (D4.3).

2.2.5 Short-term results with Economic Impact

ID 20: 5 providers and consumers of empirical evidence, share data based on specific rules through the CHORIZO ‘Insighter’ Datahub

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
20	5 providers and consumers of empirical evidence, share data based on specific rules through the CHORIZO ‘Insighter’ datahub	2,6	D2.2	M12	30 providers and consumers of empirical evidence, share data based on specific rules through the CHORIZO ‘Insighter’

The CHORIZO “Insighter” Datahub will be delivered in M12 through D2.2. Then, providers and consumers of empirical evidence will be approached with the aim to engage at least 5 to share data based on specific rules through the datahub.

Considering that 2 years after the end of the Project (medium-term outcome) it is expected that 30 providers and consumers of empirical evidence will share their data through the Datahub, the achievement of this short-term result can be evaluated as follows:

5 providers	6-10 providers	providers > 10
good	very good	excellent

ASSESEMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is very good.

A total number of 9 providers have already provided and shared the data from the CSs to the CHORIZO Insighter. The case study owners have provided information on specific rules which were shared through the datahub of CHORIZO. The following CSs were included:

CS1: Households	EV ILVO
	CNTA
CS2: Hospitality	STRAWBERRY
CS3: Food services	ITC
	PCCI
CS4: Schools	UCPH
CS5: Food Banks	HFBA
CS6: Date marking and Smart packaging	CNTA
	FIAB

ID 21: 2 companies express their formal interest for assistance services, based on the insight provided by the CHORIZO ‘Insighter’ Datahub

ID	Short-term result	Related WP	Related Del.	Due Date of Del.	Medium term Outcome
21	2 companies express their formal interest for assistance services, based on the insight provided by the CHORIZO ‘Insighter’	2, 5, 6	D2.2	M12	5 companies receive assistance services, based on the insight provided by the CHORIZO ‘Insighter’

The CHORIZO “Insighter” Datahub will be delivered in M12 through D2.2. Then, companies will be approached with the aim to engage at least 2 to receive services based on the insight provided by the “Insighter”.

Considering that 2 years after the end of the Project (medium-term outcome) it is expected that 6 companies will receive assistance services based on the insight provided by the CHORIZO “Insighter”, the achievement of this short-term result can be evaluated as follows:

2 companies	3 companies	companies > 4
good	very good	excellent

ASSESSMENT:

The result is achieved and evaluation status is excellent.

During the Bologna general assembly of the CHORIZO consortium on the 26th of February 2025, an interactive workshop was organised by the Datahub Core group team. All partners participated in the activities and a scenario-based exercise in order to provide their validation of the Datahub. We gather feedback on the usability and searchability features and the general structure of the Datahub and identified areas of improvement. All partners expressed their interest and worked on potential assistance services that could be provided by the Datahub and would be useful for their organisation. On the second EAB members meeting which was held on the 18th of March 2025, all six participating

members shared positive feedback on the work done and presented and expressed interest in using the datahub. Login credentials were provided to them to explore the Datahub and a short questionnaire was shared for their feedback. A similar session was held with two representatives from the COMBINE project with the same results.

3 IMPACT ASSESSMENT MONITORING

3.1 Impact assessment Monitoring tool

To evaluate the progress of the short-term results, CHORIZO has developed an xls monitoring tool, to provide information on the status of the short-term results and to assess their achievement. In this xls tool, every short term-result is linked to an ID (Column C), a WP (Column E), a Deliverable (Column F), and a Responsible Partner (Column E). Then, as described in Section **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**, every six months the responsible partners will have to respond if their result is achieved (Column I). If not, a description of the current status is needed (Column J), providing also information on potential obstacles and measures to overcome them, as well as an estimation of when the result will be achieved. In case the result is achieved a description of the actions taken towards achievement is needed, accompanied with an assessment of the achievement (based on the criteria that were analyzed in previous Sections (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**, **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**, 2.2.4). The CHORIZO Impact Assessment Monitoring tool is presented in Section **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** (ANNEX II).

3.2 Time-plan of monitoring progress

As previously mentioned, the progress monitoring of the results occurred every 6 months. During the first 6 months of the project, as the required deliverables have not yet been provided (as expected), the progress of the results is directly tied to the progress of the relevant deliverables. So, during this period, INLECOM and the Project Partners have established and agreed upon the monitoring and evaluation process.

- In month 12, focus will be on monitoring short-term results corresponding to the identification numbers 1, 5, 6, 8, 11, and 12.
- In month 18, the short-term results that were not completed in the previous monitoring phase will be re-evaluated, in addition to those identified by the numbers 2, 3, 4, 7, 20, and 21.
- In month 24, the focus will be on re-monitoring the short-term results that were not completed in the previous monitoring phase to provide an updated status.
- In month 30, the short-term results that were not completed in the previous monitoring phase will be re-evaluated, in addition to those identified by the numbers 9 and 10.
- In month 36, the focus will be on re-monitoring the short-term results that were not completed in the previous monitoring phase, as well as those identified by the numbers 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, and 19.

The table below indicates the start date of monitoring for each short-term result. If a result was not achieved, it was re-examined in the next monitoring phase, which took place six months later. For instance, during month 18, results with IDs 2, 3, 4, 7, 20, and 21 were monitored for the first time (marked with x), while results 1, 5, 6, 8, 11, and 12 would be evaluated only if they were not achieved in the previous monitoring phase conducted in month 12 (marked with "o").

Table 5 Start date of monitoring for each short-term result

Result ID:	Month 6 Mar 2023	Month 12 Sep 2023	Month 18 Mar 2024	Month 24 Sep 2024	Month 30 Mar 2025	Month 36 Sep 2025	
1		x	o	o	o	o	
2	Methodology design and monitoring framework.		x	o	o	o	
3			x	o	o	o	
4				x	o	o	o
5			x	o	o	o	o
6			x	o	o	o	o

Result ID:	Month 6 Mar 2023	Month 12 Sep 2023	Month 18 Mar 2024	Month 24 Sep 2024	Month 30 Mar 2025	Month 36 Sep 2025
7			x	o	o	o
8		x	o	o	o	o
9					x	o
10					x	o
11		x	o	o	o	o
12		x	o	o	o	o
13						x
14						x
15						x
16						x
17						x
18						x
19						x
20			x	o	o	o
21			x	o	o	o

4 CONCLUSION

This impact assessment confirms that CHORIZO has delivered concrete achievements across its objectives on all the domains: scientific, societal and economic/technological. Out of the 21 short term results detailed in the Grant Agreement, the majority have been reached or exceeded.

At the scientific level, the project has produced significant research in order to advance the understanding of social norms and behavioral factors and their influence on food waste. Most of the articles are submitted or published as open access, ensuring CHORIZO's commitment on open accessibility and high visibility.

At the societal level, the FLW actions database has surpassed expectations with unique views and feedback from the users. The case studies and targeted interventions have demonstrated measurable changes and reductions. The communications and education packages have gathered great interest for further adoption from schools, associations and municipalities. Finally, the capacity building programmes managed to link the research findings to the day-to-day operations of food professionals. Survey results confirm that food actors have rated all the tools positively and believe that they can help on decision-making, knowledge and more engagement.

At the economic/technological level, the tools developed, specifically the CHORIZO Datahub Insider and the OFLW Visualizer/Rapid Appraisal Tool, have been positively received from various food actors. The strong interest suggests potential for sustained use and future adoption. Furthermore, the sector specific guidance has been shared and used by multiple associations. Survey and feedback results suggest that there is strong potential for integration into organisational practices.

Overall, the project's KPIs range from very good to excellent across most metrics. Many results have exceeded the short-term targets and already achieved their medium-term outcomes. The next phase will concentrate on monitoring how the tools are used in the medium term, increase the audience and support broader use of the materials, in an effort to strengthen the connection between behavioral insights and innovation change towards zero food waste.

CHORIZO PROJECT

